

Enhancing ibuprofen solubility via a novel cocrystallization strategy: Experimental and computational insights

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Abstract

Ibuprofen (IBP), a BCS Class II drug, exhibits poor solubility and a high sticking tendency during compression in tablet manufacturing. This study presents a novel ultrasound-assisted cocrystallization method using nicotinamide (NIC) as a cofomer at a 1:1 molar ratio in acetonitrile, followed by sonication at 50 kHz for 10–60 minutes. Differential scanning calorimetry and powder X-ray diffraction confirmed the formation of a new solid phase, while microscopy revealed time-dependent changes in crystal habit. Infrared spectroscopy identified two new hydrogen-bond peaks, which correlated with density functional theory (DFT) computational analysis, confirming the presence of two intermolecular hydrogen bonds. Complexation energy, thermodynamic parameters, and frontier molecular orbital calculations further validated cocrystal stability, particularly in acetonitrile. The optimized cocrystal obtained after 60 minutes of sonication improved solubility by 1.3-fold (60.89 ± 0.74 ppm) compared with pure IBP (45.76 ± 1.04 ppm). The formulated tablets exhibited improved hardness, low friability, and no sticking. This combined experimental–computational approach demonstrates a robust and efficient strategy for enhancing the solubility and manufacturability of IBP.

Keywords

Cocrystal, ibuprofen, nicotinamide, solubility, ultrasound-assisted

Introduction

Ibuprofen (IBP) is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) that is classified as a BCS Class II compound due to its poor solubility, which results in low bioavailability (Bajpai et al. 2022; Cámara-Martínez et al. 2022). Various approaches, such as complexation, nanotechnology, spherical porous silica, and solid dispersion, have been developed to overcome this limitation (Gozali et al. 2015; Kawano et al. 2021; Naik et al. 2021; Mandati et al. 2023; Sarafska et al. 2024). In addition, ibuprofen is also known for its poor physical proper-

ties. It has a low melting point, which causes sticking during manufacturing (Dembélé et al. 2022; Le et al. 2025). Crystal properties are known to strongly affect the physicochemical characteristics of a molecule. A cocrystal is part of crystal engineering, in which two or more molecules within the same crystal lattice interact through noncovalent bonds (Erleben 2020). Consequently, cocrystallization alters crystal properties, which may modify both physical and chemical behavior. For instance, cocrystallization has been proven to improve the solubility of various active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), such as etoricoxib and carvedilol (Sopyan et al. 2023a,

2023b; Susanto et al. 2024). Moreover, it has shown substantial improvement in the physical properties of rivaroxaban and caffeine (Kale et al. 2020; Singaraju et al. 2020).

Cocrystals can be formed using several methods, with solvent-assisted grinding and solvent evaporation being the most commonly applied. Solvent-assisted grinding is a simple and effective technique that often affords high yields; however, it may lead to incomplete cocrystallization. For example, diclofenac sodium and L-proline cannot be formed using this method (Nugrahani and Auli 2020). In contrast, solvent evaporation can drive the reaction to completion, but it is not economically favorable due to high solvent consumption. Furthermore, it often results in low yields. Several modifications to crystallization techniques have been introduced to address these limitations, including microwave-induced crystallization and ultrasound-assisted cocrystallization (Nugrahani and Auli 2020; Ratih et al. 2020).

Ultrasound—an oscillating sound pressure wave with a frequency range of 15 kHz to 10 MHz—is known to positively influence crystallization processes by providing accelerated conditions (Xiang et al. 2024). The main mechanism attributed to cocrystal formation from solution under ultrasound involves cavitation induced by ultrasonic waves. The cavitation energy generated can influence nucleation phenomena in particle-free solutions. Through this mechanism, supersaturation can be achieved more readily than in conventional crystallization, in which it is often difficult to attain. In addition, cavitation energy allows low supersaturation levels to induce primary nucleation by reducing the induction period and metastable zone width (Apshingekar et al. 2017). Previous studies have demonstrated effective cocrystal formation of telmisartan using this approach, producing cocrystals with favorable mechanical properties (Ratih et al. 2020). Caffeine–maleic acid cocrystals at different molar ratios have also been successfully produced using ultrasound-assisted methods (Apshingekar et al. 2017).

The development of IBP cocrystals has been successfully achieved through several approaches. The most common method is solvent evaporation, while grinding, crystallization, and melting have also been used to produce IBP cocrystals with various cofomers (Othman et al. 2016, 2018; Dubey et al. 2025). The slurry technique has likewise been employed to produce this cocrystal (Dubey et al. 2025). Nicotinamide (NIC), in particular, has emerged as a widely used cofomer for IBP cocrystal formation. A fundamental principle of cocrystal design lies in the presence of supramolecular synthons, which are structural units formed through noncovalent interactions, such as hydrogen bonding, that act as donors or acceptors and enable stable intermolecular interactions (Susanto 2025). NIC possesses functional groups well suited for this purpose, including one hydrogen bond donor and two hydrogen bond acceptors, which can facilitate the formation of robust hydrogen-bonded synthons with IBP (National Center for Biotechnology Information 2025a). Additionally, the ΔpK_a between IBP and NIC is less than 1, a range typically indicative of cocrystal formation rather

than salt formation (Center for Drug Evaluation and Research [CDER] 2018). Beyond molecular compatibility, the safety profile of the cofomer is also critical. NIC is classified as Generally Recognized As Safe (GRAS), further supporting its suitability for pharmaceutical applications (US Food and Drug Administration 2025).

Previous work by Yuliandra et al. reported the preparation of an ibuprofen–nicotinamide (IBP–NIC) cocrystalline phase using solvent evaporation, confirming its formation by PXRD and thermal analysis and demonstrating significantly increased solubility and enhanced *in vivo* analgesic activity compared with intact ibuprofen and its physical mixture (Yuliandra et al. 2018). Similar results were reported by Chow et al., who successfully produced IBP–NIC cocrystals using solvent evaporation and observed improved physical and mechanical properties (Chow et al. 2012). Moreover, this cocrystal exhibits a spring–parachute effect, which is beneficial for enhancing the dissolution profile of poorly soluble APIs such as IBP (Wei et al. 2018). In addition, Zhao et al. characterized ibuprofen cocrystals with nicotinamide using spectroscopic and diffraction techniques, supporting the formation of new crystalline phases (Zhao et al. 2022). Ishihara et al. employed terahertz and infrared spectroscopy to elucidate intermolecular interactions during cocrystal formation, underscoring the importance of hydrogen bonding in the IBP–NIC system (Ishihara et al. 2020). Recent advances in IBP–NIC cocrystal synthesis have focused on improving efficiency and sustainability. Soares et al. introduced a green synthesis approach using aqueous media, eliminating organic solvents, and employing in-line Raman spectroscopy to monitor the reaction, thereby achieving complete conversion to the cocrystal under mild conditions (Soares and Carneiro 2013). Guerain et al. examined the polymorphism and stability of IBP–NIC cocrystals, demonstrating that different synthesis methods, including melt crystallization, co-milling, and slow evaporation, yield distinct polymorphic forms, with hydrogen bonding playing a crucial role in their formation (Guerain et al. 2020). Lin et al. proposed vapor crystallization as a solvent-free alternative, successfully preparing IBP–NIC cocrystals by sublimation of IBP and nicotinamide, offering an environmentally friendly synthesis route that overcomes solubility limitations (Lin et al. 2021).

However, there are no reports on the use of ultrasound-assisted cocrystallization for IBP–NIC systems. This method offers a more robust and faster cocrystallization process (Kim and Suslick 2018) and is considered more environmentally friendly because it requires less solvent than solvent evaporation or antisolvent methods (Xiang et al. 2024). Therefore, this study explores this alternative synthetic route to enhance cocrystal formation. In addition, previous studies have not fully established the molecular interactions within the IBP–NIC cocrystal, nor have they provided a combined experimental–computational evaluation of how these interactions influence electronic properties. This study advances the current literature by integrating experimental cocrystal preparation with solid-state characterization and computational

modeling, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the intermolecular interactions responsible for improved solubility and stability. Computational techniques are employed to predict cocrystal formation, investigate molecular interaction mechanisms, and characterize the nature of interactions between the active pharmaceutical ingredient and the coformer. These methods offer an efficient, environmentally sustainable, and scientifically robust framework for cocrystal development and rational design (Lemli et al. 2024). Accordingly, this study aims to improve the physicochemical properties of ibuprofen through a novel cocrystallization strategy, integrating computational analysis to elucidate the molecular interactions governing cocrystal formation and performance.

Materials and methods

Materials

Ibuprofen (ex. BASF, batch No. IB5D0689) and nicotinamide (ex. Western Drug Limited, batch No. 20.21/NMD[P]00069) were obtained as gift samples from PT Kalbe Farma. Spray-dried lactose, sodium starch glycolate, magnesium stearate, and talc were used as excipients in tablet formulation. HPLC-grade reagents, including acetonitrile, distilled water, chloroacetic acid, and ammonium solution, were used in the preparation of the mobile phase.

Ultrasound-assisted cocrystallization

Ibuprofen (IBP) and nicotinamide (NIC) were dissolved in a sufficient amount of acetonitrile at an equimolar ratio, with each component at a concentration of 1.615 mmol/L. The mixture was then sonicated using an ultrasonicator (Branson 1800) at 50 kHz at room temperature. The sonication time was optimized at 10, 30, and 60 minutes. The resulting solid was filtered using a suitable filter and dried at ambient temperature. The obtained cocrystals were sieved using mesh size No. 60 (250 μm) to obtain a uniform particle size distribution.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC (Shimadzu 60-Plus) was used to analyze the thermal properties of pure IBP, pure NIC, and ibuprofen cocrystals. Approximately 5 mg of each sample was weighed and placed into the DSC pan. The instrument was heated and scanned at a heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ under a nitrogen flow of 50 mL/min over a temperature range of 25–250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Data analysis was performed by plotting temperature (abscissa) versus heat flow (ordinate).

Powder X-ray diffractometry (PXRD)

Diffractogram patterns of pure IBP, pure NIC, and IBP cocrystals were obtained using a powder X-ray diffractometer (Bruker D2 Phaser). Approximately 100–

200 mg of sample was placed in the sample holder and scanned over a 2θ range of 5–40 $^{\circ}$ at a scanning speed of 8 $^{\circ}$ per minute. Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$) was used as the X-ray source.

Morphology by microscope

Crystal morphology was observed using an optical microscope (Olympus CX31) at 40 \times magnification. Crystals were examined directly on a glass slide under ambient conditions. Visual assessment was conducted to evaluate crystal shape features. Observations were performed to support solid-form characterization and detect visible variations in crystal habit. Representative images were captured to document morphology.

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

Interactions within the formed cocrystals were confirmed using FTIR spectrophotometry (Shimadzu IRTracer-100) to assess the formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonds. The attenuated total reflectance (ATR) method was employed to obtain clear and accurate infrared spectra. Approximately 5 mg of cocrystal was placed on the ATR pan, and analysis was performed over a wavenumber range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} .

Computational study

Preparation of molecules and structure parameterization

A computational study was conducted to simulate the formation of the IBP–NIC cocrystal. The computer hardware used had the following specifications: Intel Core i9-14900KF processor, 64 GB RAM, and NVIDIA RTX 4080 Super 16 GB graphics card. The computational approach employed a host–guest interaction model, in which ibuprofen (IBP) acted as the host and nicotinamide (NIC) as the guest compound. IBP and NIC molecular structures were obtained from PubChem (Kim et al. 2023), and Avogadro software was used to construct their three-dimensional structures (Hanwell et al. 2012). Geometry optimization and frequency analyses were performed using ORCA software (Jackman et al. 2019) at the B3LYP/def2-TZVP level of theory with D4 dispersion correction (Frisch et al. 2009). Structural parameter calculations were conducted to validate the computational methodology by comparing calculated structures with experimentally obtained crystal structures of IBP and NIC (Wright and Krag 1954).

Cocrystal formation

The prepared IBP and NIC molecular structures were used to construct the IBP–NIC cocrystal complex. Molecular docking simulations were performed to generate the complex using a blind docking approach, with

ORCA parameterized using GFN-xTB. A 1:1 molar ratio between host and guest molecules was applied, consistent with previous experimental findings (Yuliandra et al. 2018a). The resulting cocrystal complexes were analyzed for intermolecular interactions using Chemcraft software (Anon Chemcraft undated). Selected cocrystal structures were further optimized, and frequency analyses were conducted under vacuum and solvated conditions in ethanol and acetonitrile using the solvent model density (SMD) implicit solvation approach.

Cocrystal stability analysis

Cocrystals optimized under vacuum, ethanol, and acetonitrile conditions were evaluated for energy values and thermodynamic parameters. Complexation energy ($\Delta E_{\text{cocrystal}}$) and Gibbs free energy ($\Delta G_{\text{cocrystal}}$) were calculated using the following equations (Akmal et al. 2022):

$$\Delta E_{\text{cocrystal}} = E_{\text{cocrystal IBP-NIC}} - (E_{\text{IBP}} + E_{\text{NIC}}) \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta G_{\text{cocrystal}} = G_{\text{cocrystal IBP-NIC}} - (G_{\text{IBP}} + G_{\text{NIC}}) \quad (2)$$

The structural stability of the IBP–NIC cocrystal complex was further assessed using frontier molecular orbital (FMO) analysis, focusing on the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO). Chemcraft was used to visualize three-dimensional structures and analyze structural parameters for all complexes under vacuum and solvated conditions.

Solubility study

Solubility studies were conducted using distilled water (aquadest) at room temperature. An excess amount of each sample was added to 100 mL of aquadest in an Erlenmeyer flask. The mixture was placed on a shaker and agitated continuously for 24 hours to ensure equilibrium. After agitation, the suspension was filtered through a 0.45 μm membrane filter to remove undissolved solids. The filtrate was analyzed in triplicate using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) (Shimadzu Prominence) equipped with a UV detector. HPLC analysis was performed according to the official United States Pharmacopeia (USP) method for ibuprofen quantification (United States Pharmacopeia 2025c).

Sticking propensity

Preliminary data on sticking propensity were obtained from tablet formulations. Tablets were formulated using suitable excipients, as illustrated in Table 1, and directly compressed. The produced tablets were then evaluated for various physical parameters. Uniformity of size was assessed by measuring the thickness and diameter of 20 tablets selected at random using a calibrated vernier caliper, and the results were recorded as mean values with corresponding variability (Darusman et al. 2023). Uniformity of weight was evaluated

by individually weighing 20 tablets selected at random and calculating the average tablet mass. Individual tablet weights were compared with the average mass. The test was considered acceptable if no more than two tablets deviated from the average mass by more than $\pm 5\%$ and none deviated by more than 10% (European Pharmacopoeia 11.1 2023). Tablet hardness was determined using a tablet hardness tester (Pharma Test PTB-111E). A total of 20 tablets were randomly selected, and the crushing strength of each tablet was measured under a specified load and expressed in newtons (N). The mean hardness value and standard deviation were calculated to evaluate mechanical strength (Darusman et al. 2023). Friability was assessed using a friability tester (Pharma Test PTF-20ER). A sample of whole tablets with a total mass of approximately 6.5 g was carefully dedusted and accurately weighed before testing. The tablets were then placed in the friabilator drum and rotated at 25 rpm for 100 revolutions. After testing, the tablets were removed, dedusted, and reweighed. The percentage weight loss was calculated, and a friability value not exceeding 1.0% was considered acceptable (United States Pharmacopeia 2025b). Disintegration testing was performed using a disintegration tester (Pharma Test DIST-3). One tablet was placed in each of the six tubes of the basket-rack assembly. The apparatus was operated using water as the immersion medium, maintained at $37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. After 15 minutes, the basket-rack assembly was removed, and the tablets were examined for complete disintegration. If one or two tablets failed to disintegrate completely, the test was repeated using an additional 12 tablets (United States Pharmacopeia 2025a).

Table 1. Tablet formulation.

Material	IBP	IBP-NIC*
Ibuprofen	200 mg	–
Cocrystal	–	318.4 mg
Spray-dried lactose	q.s	q.s
Sodium starch glycolate	48 mg	48 mg
Magnesium stearate	6 mg	6 mg
Talc	6 mg	6 mg
Total	600 mg	600 mg

*all variants.

Results and discussion

Ultrasound-assisted cocrystallization

Ibuprofen is an acidic compound characterized by a carboxylic acid group in its structure, with a pKa of 4.45 (National Center for Biotechnology Information 2025b). Cocrystal prediction can be performed using the ΔpKa approach. This strategy has become popular because it offers a simpler approach and is already acknowledged by regulatory agencies (Center for Drug Evaluation and Research [CDER] 2018). A suitable cocrystal can be produced when the pKa difference be-

tween the conjugate acid of the base and the acid is < 1. Thus, NIC, with a pKa of 3.35, is a suitable coformer for an ibuprofen cocrystal (National Center for Biotechnology Information 2025a). In this study, a combination of IBP and NIC was used at an equimolar ratio with a low quantity of acetonitrile, based on the study of Chow et al. (2012). A local maximum melting temperature was observed at a mole fraction of 0.5 using a thermal composition diagram (Chow et al. 2012). A local maximum temperature reflects the complete formation of a cocrystal, which occurs after melting between each component (Neupane and Rai 2021). This combination was also confirmed in a study by Yuliandra et al., which successfully formed an IBP–NIC cocrystal at a 1:1 ratio with promising results in terms of higher analgesic activity (Yuliandra et al. 2018). The choice of solvent is discussed further in Section 3.6.3. The mixture was then subjected to ultrasound at 50 kHz, which enhanced microscale mixing and turbulence through acoustic cavitation, thereby effectively reducing the induction time. The sonication time was optimized to assess the impact of energy input duration on crystallization. A sonication duration of 10 minutes was sufficient to fully produce the cocrystal, as discussed in Sections 3.2 and 3.3. After sonication, the sample was filtered and allowed to dry at room temperature. This ultrasound-assisted cocrystallization method was completed in a short time, yielding up to 90% cocrystal, which is significantly higher than the yield reported for solvent evaporation (Yuliandra et al. 2018).

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

The thermodynamic properties of crystals were examined using DSC, also referred to as thermal analysis, to identify exothermic and endothermic changes in solid-phase combinations. Thermograms of IBP, NIC, and the IBP–NIC cocrystal were compared to identify the emergence of a new solid phase based on melting point shifts. IBP showed an endothermic peak at 79.05 °C with a heat of -133.51 J/g, whereas NIC exhibited an endothermic peak at 134.65 °C with an enthalpy of -166.40 J/g. These results are consistent with the literature. Differences in thermal behavior were observed for the 10-minute sonication sample (IBP–NIC-1), which showed an endothermic peak at 94.61 °C. Similarly, peak shifts were also observed for the cocrystals obtained after 30 minutes (IBP–NIC-2) and 60 minutes (IBP–NIC-3) of sonication, at 94.04 and 96.39 °C, respectively (Fig. 1). The newly formed solid phase exhibited a relatively higher melting point than pure IBP, which may potentially reduce sticking tendency. The shift of the endothermic peak indicates a change in the solid phase and provides strong evidence for cocrystal formation. These results are comparable to cocrystal formation via solvent evaporation, which showed a T_{max} in DTA analysis of approximately 96 °C (Yuliandra et al. 2018).

Powder X-ray diffractometry (PXRD)

PXRD analysis of multicomponent crystals aims to identify the formation of a novel crystalline phase, as each compound exhibits unique diffractogram characteristics. PXRD analysis can therefore be used to identify cocrystal formation. Comparison of the positions and intensities of diffraction peaks for pure IBP, pure NIC, and the IBP–NIC cocrystal allows determination of new crystalline phase formation. The resulting diffractogram showed characteristic crystalline peaks of the cocrystal at 2θ values of 9.51, 12.64, 15.19, 15.57, 17.67, 18.76, 20.80, 21.82, 25.07, and 34.83 (Fig. 1). An additional peak appeared at 9.51°, while several peaks observed in pure IBP, including those at 6.01° and 20.01°, were absent. Lower-intensity peaks at 22.25° from IBP and at 14.70° from NIC were also reduced. These differences in diffractogram characteristics indicate the formation of a new solid state following ultrasound-assisted crystallization. These results are consistent with previous studies. Notably, the data indicate that the cocrystal had already formed after only 10 minutes of sonication.

Figure 1. a. Calorimetry of IBP, IBP–NIC-1, IBP–NIC-2, and IBP–NIC-3; b. Diffractograms of IBP, IBP–NIC-1, IBP–NIC-2, and IBP–NIC-3.

Morphology by microscope

The crystal habit reported in prior studies using ethanol was unfavorable because the crystals were needle-shaped. Crystal habit is known to influence tabletability properties, and needle-shaped crystals typically exhibit low bonding

area and poor tabletability (Pudasaini et al. 2017). Therefore, in this study, crystal habit modification was attempted by changing the solvent. Solvent selection can influence supersaturation conditions, which may subsequently alter crystal habit (Ram et al. 2025). Further consideration of solvent effects is also supported by computational data, which are discussed later. Changing the solvent to acetonitrile produced satisfactory crystal morphology, as observed by optical microscopy. Slight differences in crystal habit were observed with variations in sonication time. IBP–NIC cocrystals exhibited rod-shaped crystals after 10 and 30 minutes of sonication. However, after 60 minutes of sonication, the crystals transformed into a plate-shaped habit (Fig. 2). Variations in sonication time impart different energy levels during crystal formation, which influence crystal growth and subsequently result in different crystal habits (Singh et al. 2024).

Figure 2. a. Crystal morphology of IBP; b. NIC; c. IBP–NIC-1; d. IBP–NIC-2; e. IBP–NIC-3.

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The IR spectra of IBP, NIC, and the IBP–NIC cocrystal were analyzed to determine the mechanism of cocrystal formation based on intermolecular hydrogen bonding. The ATR method was employed due to its simplicity and its ability to provide detailed information on intermolecular interactions within the cocrystal. The overlapping spectra are shown in Fig. 3.

Successful cocrystal formation was evidenced by the formation of hydrogen bonds between IBP and NIC. The appearance of new peaks in the FTIR spectra serves as a clear indicator of cocrystal formation, as these peaks were absent in the spectra of pure IBP and NIC, thereby supporting the

formation of a new solid phase. Two distinct intermolecular hydrogen bonds were identified between IBP and NIC, as indicated by two new peaks in the IBP–NIC cocrystal spectrum located in the –OH and –NH functional group regions (Likhitha et al. 2020). The first new peak, observed at 3180 cm^{-1} , corresponds to the interaction between the –OH group of IBP, which appears at 3100 cm^{-1} in the pure IBP spectrum, and the C = O group of NIC. This peak indicates the formation of an intermolecular hydrogen bond between IBP and NIC. The second peak, observed at 3400 cm^{-1} in the cocrystal spectrum, corresponds to the interaction between the –NH group of NIC and the C = O group of IBP. The –NH stretching vibration of NIC shifts from 3360 cm^{-1} to 3400 cm^{-1} , further confirming the formation of this intermolecular hydrogen bond. These spectral changes provide conclusive evidence for the formation of the IBP–NIC cocrystal. The nature of these interactions and their contribution to cocrystal stability are further investigated in the computational study section.

Figure 3. IR spectra of IBP, NIC, and the formed cocrystals (IBP–NIC-1, IBP–NIC-2, and IBP–NIC-3).

Computational study

Preparation of molecules and structure parameterization

The computational study began with compound preparation and structure parameterization. These steps were performed by comparing experimental crystal structures of IBP and NIC with optimized geometries obtained from computational simulations. Bond distances and bond angles showed no significant differences between experimental and calculated structures, as presented in Table 2. Accordingly, the B3LYP/def2-TZVP level of theory with D4 dispersion correction was validated for analyzing IBP–NIC host–guest interactions.

Cocrystal formation

After observing that IBP, as a host molecule, exhibits compatible interactions with NIC, as a guest molecule, leading to the formation of a cocrystal complex, a study

Table 2. Geometry parameters of IBP and NIC.

Geometry parameter	Experimental	Paper equivalence	%difference	
IBP				
Distance O1-C1	1.33	O1-C15	1.3527	1.79
Distance C1-C2	1.47	C15-C7	1.5170	3.48
Distance C2-C4	1.55	C7-C6	1.5200	1.87
Distance C4-C9	1.35	C6-C13	1.3911	3.20
Distance C6-C7	1.37	C10-C5	1.3958	1.58
Angle O1-C1-O2	119.50	O1-C15-O2	122.4620	2.48
Angle O2-C1-C2	124.60	O2-C15-C7	125.7860	0.95
Angle C1-C24-C4	108.40	C15-C7-C6	108.7530	0.33
Angle C2-C4-C5	121.60	C7-C6-C15	121.0140	0.48
Angle C5-C4-C9	118.60	C12-C6-C13	118.3650	0.20
NIC				
Distance N1-C1	1.37	N2-C6	1.3311	2.84
Distance C1-C2	1.39	C6-C4	1.3946	0.48
Distance C5-N1	1.35	C9-N2	1.3323	1.24
Distance C6-N2	1.34	C8-N3	1.3634	2.05
Distance C6-O	1.22	C8-O1	1.2181	0.09
Angle C5-N1-C1	118.40	C9-N2-C6	117.5250	0.74
Angle N1-C1-C2	121.40	N2-C6-C4	123.8270	2.00
Angle C4-C5-N1	123.40	C7-C9-N2	123.3580	0.03
Angle C1-C2-C6	122.70	C6-C4-C8	123.9890	1.05
Angle C2-C6-N2	116.80	C4-C8-N3	116.5080	0.25

was conducted to investigate cocrystal formation. In this study, an approach employing ORCA with GFN-xTB was used to examine the interactions. This method offers a balance between computational speed and reasonable accuracy, particularly for small- to medium-sized molecules, and is advantageous for initial approximation studies of host-guest complex formation (Jackman et al. 2019). GFN-xTB, a semi-empirical tight-binding method, allows rapid geometry optimization and energy calculations, making it suitable for exploring molecular docking positions. Compared with high-level quantum chemistry methods and many force-field approaches, GFN-xTB is computationally faster, enabling the exploration of a larger conformational space within a reasonable time frame. The method is parameterized to provide a reliable description of geometries, vibrational frequencies, and noncovalent interactions, including dispersion forces and hydrogen bonding (Gunawan et al. 2025). The computational results indicated that two intermolecular hydrogen bonds were formed between IBP and NIC: one between the H33 atom of IBP and O34 of NIC (corresponding to peak 1 in the FTIR spectrum at 3180 cm^{-1}) and another between O2 of IBP and H48 of NIC (corresponding to peak 2 in the FTIR spectrum at 3400 cm^{-1}), as illustrated in Fig. 4. These findings correlate with the cocrystal complex formation mechanism observed in the FTIR analysis.

The interaction behavior between IBP and NIC in the IBP-NIC cocrystal was further analyzed using QTAIM and NCI-RDG analyses. QTAIM analysis was performed to confirm the specific types of interactions identified in the previous section. Interactions were analyzed by measuring the electron density at the bond critical point

Figure 4. IBP-NIC cocrystal formation.

(BCP). The BCP represents the electron density at the saddle point, where covalent and noncovalent bonds are formed between two atoms. Espinosa proposed that electron density (ρ) and its Laplacian ($\nabla^2\rho$), total electron energy density (H_b), kinetic electron density (G_b), and local potential energy density (V_b) constitute key parameters for BCP characterization, providing substantial insight into interaction properties (Espinosa et al. 1998). Koch and Popelier proposed three AIM theory-based criteria to validate hydrogen bond properties: (a) the presence of a BCP between the donor and acceptor groups; (b) minimal electron density at the BCP [$\rho(r) = 0.0020\text{--}0.0400$ a.u.]; and (c) a positive Laplacian of electron density [$\nabla^2\rho(r) = 0.0240\text{--}0.1390$ a.u.] (Koch and Popelier 1995). Interaction strength can be categorized based on $|V/G|$ values, where weak interactions are defined as $|V/G| < 1$, moderate interactions as $|V/G| = 1\text{--}2$, and strong interactions as $|V/G| > 2$ (Kazachenko et al. 2021). An overview of the BCPs for the IBP-NIC cocrystal is shown in Fig. 5. A total of 101 BCPs were observed in the cocrystal complex. Table 3 summarizes the topological properties of the IBP-NIC cocrystal, focusing on two intermolecular BCPs identified between IBP and NIC. Both BCPs, labeled 67

Table 3. Intermolecular interaction analysis of the IBP–NIC cocrystal.

No	Interaction	BCP	Condition	P	GBCP	VBCP	HBCP	($\nabla^2\rho$)	V/G
1	33(H) - 34(O)	67	Vacuum	0.0335484477	0.0428989171	-0.0554599657	-0.0125610486	0.1213514740	1.2928057266
2	2(O) - 48(H)	75	Vacuum	0.0333697041	0.0280861204	-0.0287449114	-0.0006587910	0.1097093174	1.0234561065

Figure 5. Bond critical points of the IBP–NIC cocrystal.

and 75, were classified as hydrogen bonds according to AIM theory. Evaluation of the $|V/G|$ values indicated that the intermolecular hydrogen bonds formed in the IBP–NIC cocrystal correspond to moderate interactions.

A comprehensive overview of intermolecular interactions was further investigated using NCI–RDG analysis. The principal areas of focus in NCI–RDG are steric effects, the distribution of strong and weak interactions, and interaction topology. The results are presented as a scatter plot, and the interaction isosurface is also identified. Strong or substantial interactions are classified as follows: (a) strong intermolecular interactions, such as halogen or hydrogen bonds; and (b) intramolecular interactions, such as covalent interactions and intramolecular hydrogen bonds. Weak interactions include two types: (a) van der Waals forces caused by electron cloud polarization and (b) hydrophobic interactions such as π -stacking. In contrast, ring or angle strain causes steric effects in cyclic structures (Johnson et al. 2010). The RDG function is described by the following equation:

$$RDG(r) = \frac{1}{2(3\pi^2)^{1/3}} \frac{|\nabla\rho(r)|}{\rho(r)^{4/3}} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 6 depicts the NCI–RDG of the IBP–NIC cocrystal, determined by multiplying the electron density by the sign of the second Hessian eigenvalue ($\text{sign}(\lambda_2)\rho$). The RDG isosurface of intermolecular interactions indicates that interactions between IBP and NIC in the cocrystal complex are primarily governed by hydrogen bonding and van der Waals interactions, with two hydrogen bonds formed in the IBP–NIC cocrystal. These are illustrated by two blue interaction regions, highlighted by the purple circle in the figure. Both the QTAIM and NCI–RDG results are consistent with the cocrystal complex formation mechanism observed in the FTIR analysis.

Cocrystal stability analysis

In cocrystal formation, IBP interacts with NIC as a co-former, resulting in changes in binding affinity within the formed cocrystal complex. A stable complex with improved binding efficiency is obtained when the

Figure 6. NCI–RDG isosurface of the IBP–NIC cocrystal.

interaction between IBP and NIC is stronger, as indicated by a lower complexation energy change ($\Delta E_{\text{complex}}$). In addition to strong interaction with the partner molecule, IBP must bind spontaneously to NIC. Gibbs free energy analysis is commonly used to assess the spontaneity of a process. When the Gibbs free energy change ($\Delta G_{\text{complex}}$) is negative, the process occurs spontaneously. The results show that nearly all complexes exhibit negative complexation energy values, indicating an energy-driven process, as well as negative Gibbs free energy values, confirming that cocrystal formation occurs spontaneously (Table 4). The formed cocrystal complexes were further analyzed under vacuum and solvated conditions using ethanol and acetonitrile. Under solvated conditions, changes in ΔE and $\Delta G_{\text{complex}}$ values were observed, indicating that the solvent influences intermolecular interactions within the complex. Under vacuum conditions, only IBP and NIC molecules contribute to intermolecular interactions. In contrast, under solvated conditions, interaction potentials extend to include both solvent molecules and the cocrystal complex. The cocrystal components exhibit significant interactions with the solvent, leading to changes in intermolecular hydrogen bonding (Prasetyanto et al. 2026).

Table 4. ΔE and ΔG values of the IBP–NIC complex under vacuum and solvated conditions.

Condition	$\Delta E_{\text{cocrystal}}$	$\Delta G_{\text{cocrystal}}$
Vacuum	-17.565762	-17.56576048
Ethanol	-10.443041	-9.58025029
Acetonitrile	-10.716145	-11.57893707

The choice of solvent is critical, as it must dissolve all components without disrupting interactions during cocrystal formation. Frontier molecular orbital (FMO) analysis was applied to assess complex stability under

vacuum and solvated conditions. Stability was evaluated using the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) parameters to calculate the energy gap (Eg), hardness (η), softness (S), chemical potential (μ), and electrophilicity index (ω), derived from Koopmans' theorem and Parr functions (Parr and Chattaraj 1991; Parr et al. 1999). These descriptors provide insight into the electronic properties and reactivity of the IBP–NIC complexes (Desai et al. 2022).

$$E_g = E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO} \quad (4)$$

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} (E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO}) \quad (5)$$

$$S = \frac{1}{2\eta} \quad (6)$$

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2} (E_{HOMO} + E_{LUMO}) \quad (7)$$

$$\omega = \mu^2/2\eta \quad (8)$$

The energy gap (Eg) reflects charge transfer from the HOMO to the LUMO, with lower values indicating higher reactivity. Hardness (η) represents resistance to polarization, whereas softness (S) reflects the ease of electron acceptance and overall reactivity. Chemical potential (μ) describes the tendency of electrons to escape from a system, and the electrophilicity index (ω) measures the ability of a system to acquire additional charge (Gunawan et al. 2023). Based on the calculated FMO parameters presented in Table 5, acetonitrile was identified as the optimal solvent for complex formation between IBP and NIC.

Solubility study

The solubility of IBP in water was 45.76 ppm, which is relatively close to the theoretical value. Based on these data, solubility enhancement was observed after cocrystal formation with nicotinamide (Table 6). All cocrystal variants exhibited higher solubility compared with pure IBP. The cocrystals showed solubility increases of up to 1.3-fold relative to pure ibuprofen. This result is consistent with the study by Yulian-dra et al. (2018). Cocrystals enhance solubility through changes in molecular arrangement and lattice packing, which reduce lattice energy and improve drug solubility (Huang et al. 2022). The highest solubility was observed for IBP–NIC-3, which may be related to differences in crystal habit. Crystal habit is influenced by variations in growth rate during crystallization and plays a crucial role in determining the solubility of an active pharmaceutical ingredient, as demonstrated in studies on ticagrelor (Ren et al. 2019). Plate-shaped crystals have also been reported to exhibit improved solubility, as observed for sorafenib tosylate (Phan et al. 2021).

Sticking propensity

The cocrystal was formulated into a tablet as preliminary data to understand the sticking. The cocrystal was formulated into tablets as preliminary data to evaluate the sticking propensity of IBP and the IBP–NIC cocrystal. Tablets were formulated by adding spray-dried lactose, sodium starch glycolate, magnesium stearate, and talc, as shown in Table 1. The appearance of the tablets is presented in Fig. 7. Based on visual inspection, IBP exhibited signs of sticking even at a low batch size. In contrast, all cocrystal tablets showed improved appearance without any significant defects. These results indicate that the cocrystals exhibit more favorable physical characteristics than the parent molecule. All tablets showed uniform weight, indicating a smooth tableting process. IBP exhibited the lowest hardness

Table 5. FMO parameters of the IBP–NIC cocrystal under vacuum, ethanol, and acetonitrile conditions.

Parameter	Vacuum	Ethanol	Acetonitrile
E HOMO (eV)	-6.43826456	-6.42819627	-6.44234630
E LUMO (eV)	-1.76385591	-1.52276114	-1.53609482
Energy gap (Eg)	4.67440865	4.90543513	4.90625148
Hardness (η)	2.337204	2.452718	2.45312574
Softness (S)	0.213931	0.203856	0.20382159
Chemical potential (μ)	-4.101060	-3.9754787	-3.98922056
Electrophilicity index (ω)	19.654363	19.38190266	19.51937516

Table 6. Solubility results and physical parameter results of tablet formulations.

	IBP	IBP–NIC-1	IBP–NIC-2	IBP–NIC-3
Solubility	45.76 ± 1.04 ppm	53.70 ± 2.55 ppm	53.84 ± 2.87 ppm	60.89 ± 0.74 ppm
Uniformity of weight	596.03 ± 7.46 mg	593.12 ± 8.42 mg	598.27 ± 6.06 mg	598.29 ± 5.90 mg
Diameter	13.00 ± 0.00 mm			
Thickness	3.79 ± 0.04 mm	3.56 ± 0.08 mm	3.55 ± 0.05 mm	3.48 ± 0.04 mm
Hardness	39.42 ± 15.41 N	103.49 ± 7.93 N	86.7 ± 12.14 N	75.29 ± 10.64N
Friability	Failed	0.15%	0.15%	0.15%
Disintegration time			< 15 minutes	

Figure 7. a. Tablet appearance of IBP; b. IBP–NIC-1; c. IBP–NIC-2; d. IBP–NIC-3.

among all samples, which subsequently resulted in poor friability. The friability test failed, as substantial defects were observed during testing (Table 5). Limitations of this study include the low batch size used in the tableting process due to the limited availability of the active pharmaceutical ingredient. Evaluation using larger batch sizes should therefore be conducted in future studies. In addition, more comprehensive investigations of sticking propensity could be performed using established analytical methods (Dem-bélé et al. 2022; Le et al. 2025). The observed reduction in sticking tendency during direct compression highlights the potential of this approach to overcome manufacturing challenges commonly associated with IBP.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that ultrasound-assisted cocrystallization effectively enhances both the solubility and manufacturability of ibuprofen (IBP) using nicotinamide (NIC) as a cofomer. Equimolar IBP–NIC mixtures subjected to sonication in acetonitrile at 50 kHz for up to 60 minutes produced cocrystals with high yield (80–90%) within a short processing time. Formation of a new solid phase was confirmed by DSC and PXRD, with crystal habit changes from rod-shaped to plate-shaped observed with increasing sonication time. FTIR spectra revealed two new peaks in the –OH and –NH regions, indicating hydrogen bond formation. Computational studies further validated cocrystal formation. QTAIM and NCI–RDG analyses confirmed the presence of two intermolecular hydrogen bonds in the IBP–NIC cocrystal, which correlated with FTIR observations. The FMO approach confirmed the stability of cocrystal formation in acetonitrile, in agree-

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ment with experimental findings. The cocrystals exhibited improved solubility (up to 1.3-fold) and enhanced tablet physical properties, demonstrating that ultrasound-assisted cocrystallization is a practical and efficient strategy for improving the performance of poorly soluble drugs.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

Sharon Susanto: Project administration, Resource, Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing – original draft. Yulius Evan Christian: Methodology, Validation, Supervision Patrycia Setiawan: Data curation, Investigation. Untung Gunawan: Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Software, Project administration, Writing – review & editing.

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Data availability

All data used are referenced or included in the article.

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